

High-Performance Microfluidic Techniques toward Nanostructuring of BODIPY and BOPHY Based CPPs Hybrid Photocatalyst for Hydrogen Production

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Here, the use of high-performance microfluidic techniques (HPMT) is reported to afford conjugated porous polymer (CPPs) with smaller particle size and narrower particle size dispersion than the obtained by miniemulsion methodology. Specifically, polymers based on BODIPY or BOPHY dyes are synthesized by HPMT conditions and conventional miniemulsion conditions. The polymer textural properties from HPMT are notably improved, giving rise to high-quality thin films that are photoelectrochemically characterized. Furthermore, hybrid materials of CPPs synthesized by HPMT and TiO₂ inorganic semiconductor revealed enhanced photocatalytic activity in the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The most active hybrid UN_IEP-7@T-10 photocatalyst, containing 10 wt% polymer loading, achieved a hydrogen evolution rate of 3.10 mmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (\bar{z} = 1.13%), which is threefold higher than that of its non-nanostructured from bulk synthesis, two-times greater than its nanostructured by conventional miniemulsion techniques and even surpassed by 39-times the performance of bare TiO₂. It is noteworthy that both photoluminescence lifetime (τ_{PL}) and transient lifetime (τ_T) are not affected by the nanostructuring of CPPs, which agrees with the preservation of the chemical structure by both synthetic methodologies. The employment of HPMT as nanostructuring strategy clearly supports the obtaining of more processable polymers for a wide range of energy applications.

sources. Hydrogen energy, opens the door to one promising solution toward a sustainable alternative; which is of growing interest in the scientific community. Photocatalytic H₂ evolution has been considered a promising technology for green energy resource.^[1-6]

Therefore, developing efficient photocatalysts is of enormous importance. The past few decades have witnessed blooming development in photocatalysts, mainly focusing on inorganic semiconductors such as metal oxides and chalcogenides.^[7] However, the renaissance of organic-based semiconductors as photocatalyst has led to the development of more robust materials like porous organic materials (POPs). POPs have demonstrated their capability to be a versatile platform for efficient photocatalyst.^[8,9] POPs are covalently connected polymers that feature high specific surface area and permanent, nanometer-scale pores that are intrinsically related to exposing active sites for catalytic applications. Furthermore, they present robustness in various solvents including water, preventing corrosion, and which is favorable for the recycling process in photocatalysis.^[10] Unlike other porous

counterparts such as silicas or zeolites, POPs are designable; that is, they present a potential advantage of easy-to-tune properties through synthetic control. Thus, the nature of building blocks can be modulated by targeting different functional groups. Overall, representative POPs mainly include covalent triazine frameworks (CTFs),^[11] covalent organic frameworks (COFs)^[12-14] and conjugated porous/microporous polymers (CPPs/CMPs)^[15-18] being the last the ones presented in this work.

As mentioned above, one of the most valuable features of CPPs is that their electronic structure can be easily tuned at the molecular level by modulating the organic building block, giving unique properties to the material. In this sense, BODIPY (boron dipyrromethene) is one of the more successful fluorophores dye reported in the literature. These dyes, composed of a dipyrromethene bound to a central BF₂ unit, exhibit excellent chemical versatility as well as high photostability to be use in a wide variety of fields, from (bio)technological

1. Introduction

The increasing shortage of fossil fuel and environmental pollution have received great attention in the search for clean energy

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applications^[19–21] to solid state lasers,^[22] energy conversion in photovoltaic devices,^[23] or hydrogen production.^[24–26] BODIPY-based CPPs have been also used as heterogeneous photocatalysts in organic transformations,^[27,28] and sensing,^[29,30] among others. In fact, we have reported the synthesis of a hybrids based on BODIPY polymer networks for solar fuels production.^[14,31] On the other hand, BOPHY (boron pyrrol hydrazine) family of dyes has emerged as an analogue to BODIPY dyes.^[32,33] They present two chelating positions capable of linking BF₂ unit. In both dyes, the synthetic access involves boron chelation of a π -conjugated pyrrole-based system, but, in the BOPHY case, it includes a central hydrazine-based spacer.^[33,34] BOPHY dyes have been proven to be exceptional photoactive materials suitable for numerous research fields such as electrochemistry,^[35] and solar cells^[36,37] among others. Actually, we have described the synthesis of CPPs photocatalysts based on BOPHY as part of a photon up-conversion system,^[38] for oxidation of organic sulfides,^[39] hydrogen production^[40] and CO₂ photoreduction.^[31]

In spite of the great success of CPPs, one main drawback is related to their large particle size and the lack of processability when they come from bulk polymerization methods. In this sense, nanostructuring of CPPs by miniemulsion polymerization has proved to enhance the photocatalytic performance in the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Good deal of evidence for this behavior was given by Cooper's group, this nanopolymers presented three times higher HER performances than the corresponding bulk polymers.^[41] The miniemulsion technique is characterized in that the polymerization occurs in the hydrophobic inner environment of a micelle. However, the control over nanoparticle size with standard miniemulsion techniques remains insufficient. Therefore, this work is focussed on the improvement of this chief drawback, which have been elusive in the state-of-art. To do so, the use of high-performance microfluidic technologies (HPMT) in order to control the micelle size and distribution before polymerization step could be a solution to the problem. This kind of techniques have been broadly used in the polymerization of soft polymers for biological applications,^[42,43] but, as far as we known, there are not examples in the literature to the nanostructured CPP synthesis.

Regarding, organic–inorganic hybrids, which synergize the virtues of both organic and inorganic counterparts, have emerged as a new class of highly versatile functional materials with tailored properties and enhanced energy conversion efficiency.^[44,45] Very recently, our research group has demonstrated the boosted synergetic effect between nanostructured phenylene vinylene-based CPPs and TiO₂ nanocrystals. The beneficial effects of a nanostructuring strategy in the photocatalytic activity for solar fuels production is a result of a better interplay between the components that are in intimate contact in the hybrid heterostructure.^[46]

Herein, we have found that the combined use of miniemulsion techniques and high-performance microfluidic technologies remarkably afforded nanostructured CPPs, not only having smaller particle size but also lower particle size dispersity. In particular, we report the synthesis of BODIPY and BOPHY-based CPPs and hybrid thereof and the favorable impact of an “ultra-nanostructuring” strategy in the photocatalytic hydrogen production reaction. The reduced particle size is translated into the higher external surface area that drive to a better interaction be-

tween the semiconducting counterparts leading to an enhancement in the photocatalytic performance. Furthermore, the reduction of CPP nanoparticle size lead to an unaltered Type II charge transfer mechanism determined by means spectroscopic studies, being the transient lifetime the same as the recorded in bulk.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design, Synthesis, and Characterization of (Ultra)Nanostructured CPPs

Herein, a new miniemulsion polymerization method thought high-performance microfluidic techniques (HPMT) is described. Thus, we have found that the combined use of miniemulsion techniques and high-performance microfluidic technologies remarkably provided nanostructured CPPs, not only presenting smaller particle size but also lower particle size dispersity. With this aim, in the present work we have synthesized both Nano_CPPs from conventional miniemulsion conditions and UltraNano_CPPs (UN_CPPs) from ultra-mini-emulsion conditions in order to compare their textural properties as well as their photocatalytic performances.

On one hand, BODIPY and BOPHY based Nano_CPPs, Nano_CMPBDP, and Nano_IEP-7, respectively, were prepared from the respective monomers by Pd(0)-catalysed Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction (Figure 1A) in miniemulsions conditions (Figure 1B). In all cases, the monomers, [Pd(PPh₃)₄] and CuI were dissolved in toluene: trimethylamine (1:1). Then, the organic phase was added to an aqueous solution of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (1 wt%). The reaction mixture was then sonicated for 10 min to give miniemulsions of toluene droplets stabilized by CTAB in water. These miniemulsions were then subjected to solvothermal treatment polymerization conducted according to previously described procedures^[46–48]

On the other hand, UltraNano_CPPs (UN_CPPs) analogues, UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7, were synthesized in ultra-mini-emulsions thought HPMT (Figure 1C). The synthetic procedure is pretty similar as the above describe for obtaining Nano_CPPs. However, it presents the following singularity: right after applying 10 min of sonication, the mini-emulsions obtained, were pass through a microfluidizer equipment (Figure S1, Supporting Information), to get further reduced and better controlled sizes and dispersity of the ultra-mini-emulsions obtained (Figure 1C). Then, these reaction mixtures were subjected to solvothermal treatment polymerization. It is important to note that this synthetic procedure was first described and protected by a European Patent for our research group.^[49]

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) and solid-state ¹³C cross-polarization magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance (CP-MAS NMR) data collected for Nano_CPPs and UN_CPPs, clearly support that the chemical structures are not affected by any synthetic methodology, neither miniemulsion nor ultra-miniemulsion. CMPBP and IEP-7 polymers were previously synthesized in our research group using conventional bulk synthetic techniques,^[27,40] and their chemical structures perfectly math the ones presented in the present study.

FTIR spectra shown in Figure S7 (Supporting Information) confirm the formation of both polymers by the presence of the

Figure 1. General scheme for the synthesis of nanostructured CMPBDP and IEP-7 polymers by Sonogashira reaction (The reaction conditions indicated are: a) CuI/Pd(PPh₃)₄ in Toluene/Et₃N and CTAB aq. 1 wt% and thermal treatment). Downside: cartoons explaining differences between synthesis of Nano_CPPs B) and the synthesis on UN_CPPs C) using high-performance microfluidic techniques.

—C≡C— stretching band at ca. 2198 cm⁻¹ and the disappearance of the band corresponding to a terminal alkyne (—C≡C—H), which gives rise to a sharp band centred at ≈3300 cm⁻¹. Additionally, the presence of a C=N stretching band located at ca. 1650 cm⁻¹ characteristic from BODIPY (CMPBDP) and BOPHY (IEP-7) structures, also appeared. Furthermore, FTIR spectra exhibit two bands ≈2917 and 2846 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the =C—H stretching in both polymers.

Solid-state ¹³C NMR spectra also confirmed the formation of the triple bond in all polymers showing well-defined peaks at ca. 90 ppm corresponding to —C≡C—. Peaks centered at 7–11 ppm, correlate to aliphatic carbons and peaks located between 120 and 140 ppm are characteristic to the aromatic carbons. In addition, signals placed between 29 and 52 ppm that correspond to the CTAB structure are also observed, indicating that the surfactant is embedded in the structures, despite the polymer samples were

washed thoroughly with water (Figure S8, Supporting Information).

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements for the dispersions obtained by miniemulsion polymerization showed no material larger than 1.5 μm in hydrodynamic size (Figure 2; Table S2, Supporting Information). In the case of Nano_CPPs the population was split into two main groups with average hydrodynamic diameters of 260 ± 50 nm and 1010 ± 160 nm for Nano_CMPBDP, while 216 ± 60 nm and 619 ± 200 nm were observed for Nano_IEP-7. By contrast, particles obtained by ultra-mini-emulsion polymerization does not show any material >200 nm in hydrodynamic size (Figure 2), exhibiting average hydrodynamic diameters of 143 ± 17 nm, 142 ± 15 nm for UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7, respectively. As result, the Nano_CPPs particles, showed no signs of aggregation over 7 days without stirring, with negligible changes in average particle

Figure 2. A) FESEM image of Nano_IIEP-7 (left side); DLS data showing size distribution for Nano_IIEP-7 and UN_IIEP-7 in freshly distilled Milli-Q H₂O (middle) and FESEM image of UN_IIEP-7 (right side). B) Aqueous dispersions appearance of Nano_CMPBDP (left) and UN_CMPBDP (right); Nano_CMPBDP reveals sign of aggregation 7 days after its chemical synthesis, whereas UN_CMPBDP does not show any sign of aggregation after >2 months after its chemical synthesis. C) FESEM image of Nano_CMPBDP (left side); DLS data showing size distribution for Nano_CMPBDP and UN_CMPBDP in freshly distilled Milli-Q H₂O (middle) and FESEM image of UN_IIEP-7 (right side).

diameter or size polydispersity as measured by DLS (Figure S9, Supporting Information). While, UN_CPPs particles kept stable with no sign of aggregation for >2 months (Figure 2B for CMPBDP and Figure S10, Supporting Information, for UN_IIEP-7) as it is confirmed by DLS (Figure S11, Supporting Information). In order to confirm the results from DLS, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken. Nano_CPPs materials depicted in Figure 2 left and Figure S12 (Supporting Information) show irregular particle sizes with distributions between 20–130 nm. At the same time, UN_CPPs FESEM images (Figure 2 right and Figures S13 and S14, Supporting Information) reveal smaller and extremely homogeneous nanospheres, ca. 24 ± 3 nm and 22 ± 4 nm for UN_CMPBDP and UN_IIEP-7, respectively (size histograms depicted at Figures S13 and S14, Supporting Information). This is also confirmed by TEM images (Figure S15, Supporting Information for UN_CMPBDP and Figure S16, Supporting Information for UN_IIEP-7). Note that the average particle size and particles size distribution taken with microscopy

techniques are smaller and narrower than those measured with DLS since the second correspond to the hydrodynamic diameters.

With these data in hand, we confirm that the main advance of the ultra-mini-emulsion lies in the application of high-performance microfluidics technologies to the production of CPPs nanoparticles with lower particle size and low dispersity.

The textural properties of Nano_CPPs and UN_CPPs were evaluated by means of N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherms (Figure S17, Supporting Information). Each surface area was calculated by BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) theory. Thus, Nano_ and UN_CPPs exhibit higher BET values than the ones observed for the analogous polymers synthesized by bulk methodology (Table S2, Supporting Information; Figure 3). IIEP-7 series present an interesting behavior: while IIEP-7 synthesized by bulk conventional techniques showed modest surface areas (ca. $56 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Table S2, Supporting Information), both nanostructured polymers showed and appreciable increased of surface area (ca. 227 and $280 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, for Nano_IIEP-7 and UN_IIEP-7, respectively).

Figure 3. Percentages of microporosity/external surface area for Bulk_IEP-7, Nano_IEP-7, UN_IEP-7, Bulk_CMPBDP, Nano_CMPBDP and UN_CMPBDP; data of Bulk_CPPs is extracted from references 31 and 41.

BOPHY core presents almost the same orthogonality than BODIPY architecture. However, the first is larger than the last. The longer length of BOPHY allows the interpenetration between the polymer branches avoiding the polymeric laminar formation which can explain the lower porosity observed for bulk IEP-7.^[40] For the same reason, the microporosity in the whole IEP-7 series is negligible. So, the increase in the overall surface area from bulk to ultraminiemulsion passing through miniemulsion sample is only due to the external surface area increase by the decrease in the size (Figure 3).

On the other hand, since bulk CMPBDP shows a surface area of *ca.* 299 m² g⁻¹, the nanostructuring does not affect to the BET surface area in the same extension in the BODIPY series (Figure 3). Here, the nanostructured samples exhibit a slight improvement (*ca.* 350 ± 5 m² g⁻¹ for both samples) but the percentage of the external surface area is more evident in UN_CMPBDP than in Nano_CMPBDP, increasing up to 71%. The pore size distributions were estimated with non-local density functional theory (NLDFT). They are plotted in Figure S18 (Supporting Information) where it is seen that UN_CMPBDP present a dual porosity with the majority of pores lower than 2 nm but also a small fraction of pores in the range from 2 to 25 nm.

The thermal stabilities of Nano_ and UN_CPPs were studied by thermogravimetric analysis under air and argon atmospheres (Figures S19 and S20, Supporting Information). Nano_ and UN_CPPs under inert atmosphere showed incomplete degradation and high thermostability. On the other side, the thermograms under air shows a complete mass loss at 500 °C for UN_ and Nano_CMPBDP; a value slightly lower, *ca.* 400 °C, was observed for UN_ and Nano_IEP-7. In all cases the onset was found at *ca.* 200 °C, slightly lower than the respective bulk materials.^[27,40]

The nanostructured morphology of Nano_ and UN_CPPs dispersions, enabled the preparation of high-quality thin films in or-

der to perform accurate photoelectrochemical characterization. In this regard, electrodes have been prepared over Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) support by spin-coating technique (Figure S21A,B, Supporting Information). FESEM images reveals thin, homogeneous and high-quality films from UN_CPPs dispersions (Figure S21B, Supporting Information). Lack of this homogeneity was observed in the case of the films prepared from Nano_CPPs dispersions, as it is showed by the appearance of some cracks (FESEM Figure S21B, Supporting Information), being able to carry out scarce electrochemical characterization (OCP measurements are shown in Figure S22, Supporting Information). In contrast, for UN_CPPs films, and thanks to its improved quality, an extensive electrochemical characterization was performed (Figure 4). In this line, cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements (Figure 4A,C) were carried out to determine the electronic structure of the polymers (Figure 4B). The position of the HOMO and LUMO were estimated in -5.41 ± 0.05 and -3.27 ± 0.05 eV for UN_CMPBDP and -5.30 ± 0.05 and -3.02 ± 0.05 eV for UN_IEP-7. Therefore, their band gap values are 2.1 ± 0.1 eV and 2.3 ± 0.1 eV, respectively. Furthermore, these values were studied by diffuse reflectance (Figure S23, Supporting Information). UV-vis absorption confirms that the UN_CPPs possess a direct transition with optical bandgaps of 1.9 ± 0.1 eV and 2.3 ± 0.1 eV for UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7 respectively, slightly smaller than the electronic ones as expected.^[50,51]

By evaluating the energy diagram obtained for UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7, we observe that we have two p-type semiconductors whose Fermi level is not very close to the valence band but rather at half the energy of the bandgap, more typical characteristic of an intrinsic semiconductor. This means that it is not a non-heavily doped semiconductor, a feature previously observed in other CPPs.^[46,52]

Photoelectrochemical measurements confirm this statement. The p-type conductivity was confirmed by the open circuit potential (OCP) measurements (Figure 4D,G), showing an increase in the signal under illumination.^[52] In this sense, the photoresponses of both electrodes were measured under illumination in OCP, and were found to be 85 and 72 mV for UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7, respectively. However, LSV measurements (Figure 4E,H) exhibited both positive and negative photocurrents. This behavior opens the door for these materials to be used in both oxidation and reduction reactions, as in fact has been done previously.^[52] In fact, this possibility of conduction by both electrons and holes explains that this CPPs, which in principle has a p-type conductivity, can carry out also the oxidation reaction, as will corroborated through the mechanistic study carried out after by TAS.

Furthermore, since UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7 present positive and negative photoresponses in the linear sweep voltammetry this fact correlates with the position of the Fermi level, which is determined by the flat band potential. The energy of the flat band potential was determined as the point in which positive photocurrents changes to negative ones, since at this potential there is no band bending. Thus, the energy of the Fermi level is $E_F = -4.63$ eV for UN_CMPBDP and $E_F = -4.64$ eV for UN_IEP-7.

Regarding chronoamperometric measurements (Figure 4F,I), the cell was illuminated with on/off cycles with regular intervals. Both polymers, UN_CMPBDP (Figure 4C) and UN_IEP-7 (Figure 4F) present a stable photocurrent. UN_CMPBDP

Figure 4. Photoelectrochemical measurements of polymers UN_CMPBDP (in blue) and UN_IEP-7 (in green). A,C) Cyclic voltammetry measurements in non-aqueous electrolyte at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . B) Electronic band structure of both UN_CMPBDP and UN_IEP-7 where as black line is the Fermi level of each semiconductor and as dash lines the redox pair of reactive and products. D,G) photovoltage measures in open circuit potential condition. E,H) Linear sweep voltammetry under chopped illumination showing the photocurrent density at different bias potentials. F,I) Chronoamperometry at -0.6 and -1.0 V, respectively, bias potential under chopped illumination.

exhibit photogenerated current densities of ca. $-0.18 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at -0.6 V; whereas, the photogenerated current densities of ca. $-0.26 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at -1.0 V were observed for UN_IEP-7.

2.2. Preparation of Hybrid Materials

Here we have investigated the effect of CPP ultra-nanostructuring in the hybrid heterojunctions based on them and an inorganic semiconductor for photocatalytic applications, specifically in the hydrogen evolution reaction. TiO_2 (PC500, anatase phase) was the inorganic semiconductor selected. TiO_2 is a very well-known photocatalyst that is considered a benchmark in the field and it is usually used as inorganic counterpart in the organic-inorganic hybrid design.^[16,44] Also, its selection is due to the knowledge acquired in our previous works. For instance,

TiO_2 -based hybrid from bulk synthesized BODIPY and BOPHY CPPs polymers have been reported for us as photocatalyst for solar fuels production.^[31,40] In both cases, a synergy between both organic and inorganic counterpart was demonstrated due to a Type II charge transfer mechanism.

Thus, hybrid materials were prepared adding the dispersion of Nano_CPPs or UN_CPP to a likewise TiO_2 dispersion at 10 wt% of polymer loading, named as (Nano or UN)_CMPBDP@T-10 and (Nano or UN)_IEP-7@T-10 (see synthesis of hybrid material in experimental section for more details).

The morphology of the hybrid systems was determined by FE-SEM (see Figure 5 for UN_CMPBDP@T-10 and Figure S24, Supporting Information, for UN_IEP-7@T-10). Since the UN_CPPs nanoparticles present sizes in the same range of magnitude that TiO_2 , microanalysis by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and back scattered electrons detection were necessary

Figure 5. Morphological characterization of UN_CMPBDP@T-10. Hybrid aggregate image taken by A) FESEM. B) FESEM back scattered electrons detection mode. C) HRSEM and its magnification in (D). E) EDX mapping being Ti atoms (yellow), O atoms (green), and C atoms (purple).

to confirming the outer deposition of TiO_2 over the polymeric nanoparticles, even so, some places where the polymer is necked were also observed.

2.3. Photocatalytic Activity for H_2 Production

The photocatalytic activity of hybrid materials based on TiO_2 , was evaluated in the hydrogen production from water using methanol as reductant.

First, the photocatalytic activity of UN_CPPs was evaluated. Notice that the ultra-nanostructuring in both families does not

improve the photocatalytic activity previously reported for the bulk materials (Table 1). However, hybrid photocatalysts show remarkably synergetic effect between the organic and the inorganic counterparts in the heterojunction (Figure 6 and Table 1, Supporting Information). UN_CMPBDP@T-10, resulted in a hydrogen evolution rate of $\approx 2.96 \text{ mmol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ ($\xi = 1.09\%$), which is >33 and 37 times greater than those of bare UN_CMPBDP and TiO_2 . While, UN_IEP-7@T-10 (ca. $3.10 \text{ mmol h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$, $\xi = 1.13\%$) boosted up to 26 and 39 -fold the hydrogen production rate of bare UN_IEP-7 and TiO_2 , respectively.

The two methodologies described in this work to synthesize nanostructured polymers derived in two different hybrid

Figure 6. Cumulated hydrogen production per gram versus reaction time of A) CMPBDP hybrid photocatalysts and B) IEP-7 based hybrid photocatalysts.

materials, which led to an improvement in the HER compared to their analogue's hybrids from bulk (entries 3, 4, 6 and 7, Table 1). Between them, hybrid materials formed from the UN_CPPs showed higher hydrogen production. This agrees with a better synergy between both materials due to an increased external surface contact between both semiconductors from bulk to UN_CPP passing through Nano_CPP. The best example for this was UN_IEP-7@T10 (ca. 3.10 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 1.13%), with two-fold higher HER than Nano_IEP-7@T-10 (ca. 1.52 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 0.56%) and 3-fold increase in HER compared to Bulk_IEP-7@T-10 (ca. 0.96 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 0.36%) (Table 1, Figure 6B). On the other hand, ultra-nanostructuring improved UN_CMPBDP@T-10 performance making it 2.5 times more active (ca. 2.96 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 1.09%) than bulk CMPBDP@T-10 hybrid material (ca. 1.21 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 0.45%) and Nano_CMBDP (ca. 1.23 mmol h⁻¹, $\bar{\xi}$ = 0.46%) (Table 1 and Figure 6A).

These are remarkable results, which highlight the importance of ultra-nanostructuring of CPPs in the photocatalytic activity for the hydrogen production reaction.

Table 1. H₂ Production and photonic efficiencies.

Entry ^{a)}	Compound	H ₂ Production [mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]	Photonic efficiency, $\bar{\xi}$ [%]
1	TiO ₂ ^{b)}	0.08	0.03
	Bulk_CMPBDP ^{b)}	0.09	0.03
2	UN_CMPBDP	0.09	0.03
3	Bulk_CMPBDP@T10 ^{c)}	1.21	0.45
4	Nano_CMPBDP@T10	1.23	0.46
5	UN_CMPBDP@T10	2.96	1.09
	Bulk_IEP-7 ^{c)}	0.17	0.04
6	UN_IEP-7	0.12	0.04
7	Bulk_IEP-7@T10 ^{c)}	0.96	0.36
8	Nano_IEP-7@T10	1.52	0.56
9	UN_IEP-7@T10	3.10	1.13

^{a)} Lab-scale reaction conditions: 25 mg of catalyst on 130 mL of a methanol aqueous solution (10 vol%) at atmospheric pressure and 20 °C, irradiated by a 150 W medium-pressure Hg immersion lamp; ^{b)} Data included for comparative purposes; ^{c)} Data extracted from reference.^[40]

The photochemical stability of UN_CMPBDP@T-10, was studied in a recycling experiment: After a first photocatalytic run of 5 h of UV illumination, the hybrid material was filtered and re-dispersed to be reused in a long cycle of 25 h (Figure S26, Supporting Information). No activity decrease was observed, which demonstrates that the robust UN_CMPBDP structure confers excellent photostability to the hybrid to be reusable. Moreover, the structural stability was confirmed by means of FTIR spectra before and after the photocatalytic tests (Figure S27, Supporting Information).

2.4. Photophysical Studies

With the aim of understanding the influence of ultra-nanostructuring on the excited state properties we carried out spectroscopic studies from the ns to μ s timescale, using both steady-state and time-resolved photoluminescence (PL and TRPL, respectively) as well as transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS). To corroborate if the charge dynamics pathways in the UN_CPPs@T10 hybrid photocatalysts, is in agreement with the Type II heterojunction mechanism (Figure S28, Supporting Information) previously reported for their Bulk CPPs analogues;^[31,40] first, we measured both PL and TRPL for naked TiO₂ and hybrids in solid state (Figure 7A). We observed that the steady-state emission of TiO₂ was quenched due to the presence of UN_CMPBDP or UN_IEP-7 polymers in the hybrids, whereas the corresponding lifetimes (τ_{PL}) showed an opposite behavior (Figure 7A inset). This was associated with a filter effect instead of a real quenching since both TiO₂ and the CPPs absorb UV-light. All hybrids showed a slight increase of ≈ 100 ps τ_{PL} respect to bare TiO₂ (Figure 7A; Figure S29, Supporting Information), which agrees with a Type II heterojunction according to our previous works.^[12,14,31,40,53]

Then, bare TiO₂ and UN_CPPs hybrids dispersed in aqueous solutions containing 10% methanol (v/v) as hole scavenger,^[54] were also analysed by means of TAS. After laser excitation at 355 nm, TiO₂ showed a continuous transient absorption spectrum in all visible window. This spectrum exhibits a small band centred at ≈ 460 nm (Figure 7B), which is mainly assigned to photoelectrons after electron-hole (e⁻-h⁺) separation^[55,56] presenting a bi-exponential transient lifetime (τ_{TA}) of 50 ns and ≈ 1 μ s,

Figure 7. A) Solid-state photoluminescence decay traces and spectra (inset) for TiO₂ (grey) and hybrids UN_IEP-7@T-10 (green) and UN_CMPBDP@T-10 (blue). B) Transient absorption spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355$ nm) for TiO₂ (grey) and hybrids UN_IEP-7@T-10 (green) and UN_CMPBDP@T-10 (blue) at different timescales (0, 0.1, and 3 μs after pulse). All measurements were recorded in deaerated 10 vol% aqueous methanol suspensions. C) Corresponding transient absorption lifetimes ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{obs}} = 460$ nm) for TiO₂ (grey) and hybrids UN_IEP-7@T-10 (green) and UN_CMPBDP@T-10 (blue). Bulk polymers IEP-7@T-10 (light green) and CMPBDP@T-10 (light blue) are included for comparison. D) Hydrogen production from water splitting reactions versus transient lifetime for TiO₂ (grey) and Nano- (\diamond) or Ultra-Nano- (\star) hybrid heterojunctions based on BOPHY or BODIPY. Others hybrid heterojunctions reported by our group such as those based on BODIPY dyes (CMPBDP@T-10),^[31] BOPHY dyes (IEP-x@T-10 X = 7, 8, 9, and 10)^[40] and truxene moiety (TxPP2@T-10)^[53] have been included for comparison (\bullet).

respectively (Figure 7C; Figure S30, Supporting Information). For UN_CMPBDP@T-10 and UN_IEP-7@T-10 hybrid materials, a decrease in the e^-h^+ recombination was observed as a result of an increment in the ΔOD (Figure 7B) and transient lifetime (Figure 7C; Figure S31, Supporting Information).

Remarkably, we observed well-defined bands centred at ≈ 460 nm for UN_CPPs hybrid dispersions (Figure 7B), fact that was harder to observe for their hybrid analogues synthesized by bulk techniques,^[31] corroborating again their improved dispersion ability. Moreover, and thanks to the enhanced dispersions stability of bare UN_CPPs, we were able to perform TAS of the CPPs aqueous dispersions, exhibiting low absorptions from 500 nm under our measurement conditions (Figure S32, Supporting Information). It is worth notice that the first transient contribution for UN_CMPBDP@T-10 and UN_IEP-7@T-10 hybrids exhibited an enhancement of the transient lifetime (up to ≈ 2.3 -times greater τ_{TA}) compared to bare titania but equal to the transient lifetime of hybrid from bulk polymers reported before (Figure 7C; Figure S31, Supporting Information).^[31] This means that not only the charge transfer mechanism takes place through a Type II heterojunction mechanism but also that the nanostructuring of the polymers does not affect said mechanism.

In previous works we were able to establish a linear correlation ship between the hydrogen production and the transient lifetime

from CPPs/TiO₂ hybrid when the CPPs come from bulk synthesis conditions and the charge transfer mechanism is type II (red fitting line at Figure 7D).^[31,40,53] Here, we can see that the nano- and ultranano-structuration lead to an increase of the hydrogen production being the transient lifetime unaltered. Thus, the improve in the photocatalytic performance only can be attributed to a better and more efficient interface between both semiconductors, CPPs and TiO₂, due to an increase in the external surface area.

3. Conclusion

The use of high-performance microfluidic techniques has demonstrated to be a key tool to synthesize smaller CPPs particles with narrower particle size dispersion than those obtained from regular miniemulsion techniques. These features have stand out in the hybrid heterojunctions boosting their photocatalytic performances in the hydrogen evolution reaction. The initial hypothesis has been exemplified with the synthesis of two BODIPY and BOPHY based CPPs, by both miniemulsion and ultra-miniemulsion techniques. These nanostructured materials have been extensively characterized, being even successful to accomplish the photoelectronic characterization for the ultra-nanostructured polymers, UN_CPPs. Thus, a *p*-type conductivity

was confirmed for both UN_CPPs, be able to design a *p-n* heterojunction hybrid material using TiO₂ as *n*-type semiconductor. The hybrid material from ultra-nanostructured IEP-7 shows three times higher hydrogen production than its bulk analogue, while 2.5-folds greater productions were observed for the case of UN_CMPBDP@T-10 photocatalyst.

Spectroscopic studies, corroborate that the charge transfer mechanism is the same as the observed in hybrid from bulk synthesis. In this case, a type II charge transfer mechanism is responsible for the synergetic effect between BODIPY and BOPHY polymers and TiO₂. The improvement in the photocatalytic performance has been unlinked from an improvement in the charge transfer, being the increase in the external surface area of the polymer the responsible. In other words, as lower is the particle size greater is the contact with TiO₂ and higher the hydrogen production being equal the transient lifetime.

4. Experimental Section

Preparation of Photocatalyst: General procedure for the Synthesis of UltraNanoCPPs (UN_CPPs): The monomers (1,3,5-triethynylbenzene (1.5 mmol) and diiodo-BODIPY or diiodo-BOPHY (2 mmol)) were dissolved in toluene (5.5 mL) and triethylamine (5.5 mL) and degassed by argon bubbling for 10 min. An aqueous solution (80 mL) of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (1 wt%) was degassed by argon bubbling for 10 min. [Pd(PPh₃)₄] (0.05 mmol) and CuI (0.10 mmol) was added to the organic phase. The organic phase was added dropwise to the aqueous solution at the same time that the mixture was subjected to sonication with a UP400S Ultrasonic Processor at 50–60% power for 10 min. The miniemulsion obtained was then pass several times through a microfluidizer equipment (LM20 Microfluidizer High Shear Fluid Processor, Figure S1, Supporting Information) to give an ultra miniemulsion. The number of times was determined monitoring the size and dispersion of the obtained micelles by dynamic light scattering (DLS). In both cases, four cycles were needed for ca. 100 nm hydrodynamic radius. The obtained ultra-mini-emulsion was degassed for further 20 min. Afterward, the mixture was heated to 80 °C for 3 h under reflux. Later, the ultra miniemulsion was placed into an autoclave which was heated to 150 °C to carry out the polymerization. The emulsion was subjected to dialysis (Regenerated Cellulose Dialysis Tubing, 12–14 kDa) adding NaCN to the dialysis tube in order to remove the excess of Pd (see Table S1, Supporting Information) and using as solvent mixture first THF/H₂O (1:1) to ensure the removal of the starting material excess and second H₂O to obtain the final pure aqueous dispersion of UN_CPPs ready to be used in the photocatalytic experiments. Moreover, aliquots and UN_CPPs emulsions were filtered, washed and dried in order to perform their structural characterization.

Synthesis of Hybrid Material: For the preparation of hybrid materials, first, TiO₂ (PC500) was calcined at 400 °C for 4 h in order to remove all the possible organic impurities. Following the procedure previously described,^[46] the appropriate volume of CPP dispersion (10 wt% of CPP loading) was added to a TiO₂ (90 wt%) containing methanol/ water suspension. The resulting mixture was then stirred for 15 min until a consistent dispersion was achieved.

Photoelectrochemical Characterization: For the preparation of thin films photoelectrodes, 1 mL of each polymeric aqueous dispersion was centrifuged. The polymers were then dispersed in isopropanol (ca. 7.15 g L⁻¹) with an ultrasound tip for 5 min. Subsequently, 10 μL of each polymer dispersion was deposited by spin-coating three times on ITO cover glasses, used as working electrodes. Experiments were performed in a three-electrode glass cell with a quartz window containing an aqueous solution of 0.5 M Na₂SO₃ for photoelectrochemical measurements and 0.1 M of [(ⁿBu)₄N]PF₆ in acetonitrile for electrochemical characterization. The counter electrode was a platinum wire, and the reference one was an Ag/AgCl electrode. Voltage and current density experiments (at dark and under illumination) were measured with a potentiostat-galvanostat PG-

STAT204 provided with an integrated impedance module FRA11 (10 mV of modulation amplitude is used at 400 Hz). A solar Simulator (LOT LSH302 Xe lamp and a LSZ389 AM1.5 Global filter) calibrated as 1 Sun (100 mW cm⁻²) was used as a light source. The exposed area of the photoelectrode to the electrolyte was 1 cm².

Photocatalytic Hydrogen Production Experiments: Photocatalytic experiments were performed in a Pyrex glass double-walled reactor, which consisted of a three-mouth cylindrical flask with an effective volume of 130 mL. For the experiments, the appropriate volume of CPP dispersion (10 wt% of CPP loading) was added to a TiO₂ (90 wt%) suspension 10 vol.% methanol aqueous solution. The reactor was tightly closed and maintained at atmospheric pressure and at 20 °C by recirculating water from a cooling system. Argon was flowed through the suspension at 60 mL min⁻¹ to purge the system and to act as carrier gas. The suspension was magnetically stirred in the dark until air was removed (verified by GC) and then irradiated by a 150 W medium-pressure Hg immersion lamp (Figure S25, Supporting Information). H₂ evolution was monitored every ca. 3 min by means of an Agilent 490 micro-GC equipped with a molecular sieve column and a TCD detector.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

M.L. and V.P.O. conceived the idea and supervised the work. T.N. supervised to S.P.R. who synthesized and characterized the materials and carried out and analysed the photocatalytic H₂ evolution tests. M.B. supervised to S.P.R. who performed the electrochemical and photoelectrochemical measurements. M.G.M. performed the charge dynamics studies. T.N. and S.P.R. wrote the manuscript draft. M.L. and V.A.P.O. wrote the manuscript and discussed the results with all the contributing authors.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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